

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

U.G'.Otabekov

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN ENGINEERING SCIENCES AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS

DISCIPLINES BASED ON A PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir: A.A. Abdurahmonov

Яндекс

@mail

Google

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